

MONETARY POLICY COORDINATION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of monetary policy coordination on economic growth in Nigeria. The study incorporates current realities in the time period of 2002 Q1 to 2022 Q4. The motivation behind this study is premised on the fluctuation in economic performance in Nigeria as the main monetary policy variables change over time. The variables used for the study include the monetary policy rate, money supply, exchange rate, and real gross domestic product. The pre-estimation test was done using both the Augmented Dickey Fuller Test (ADF) and the Phillip Peron Test (PP). The main estimator used for the study is structural vector autoregressive (SVAR) techniques by estimating the structural factorization carried out by imposing certain restrictions on matrix A (the matrix that speaks to the contemporaneous relationship between the endogenous variables) based on economic intuition. The test statistics shows that the monetary policy rate has a positive and insignificant impact on output in Nigeria, the money supply was found to have a negative and significant impact on real GDP, the money supply shock contributes at least 11% to the variability in real GDP, and the appreciation of the exchange rate of the naira insignificantly promotes growth in real GDP. Conclusively, the growth of the Nigerian economy is dependent on impulses generated by the implementation of monetary policy. The study recommends that the policy direction of the apex bank should be toward reducing the monetary policy rate (MPR), as this will make credit available to real sector investors and resolve the credit constraint militating output expansion, and the Central Bank of Nigeria should implement policies to address the frequent fluctuations in the exchange rate value of the naira to protect investors.

Introduction

Prior to the discovery of black gold in exportable quantities, agriculture and manufacturing sectors had been the mainstay of the economy, contributing about 90 percent of the country's foreign exchange and playing a crucial role in fostering

economic growth. Due to the calamitous structure of the economy (because it is a single-product economy), its frailty has been exposed to swings in the international oil market, creating an unpleasant business cycle (Adeleye et al., 2015). In 2016, the Nigerian economy slipped into recession with consecutive negative growth of 0.36 percent and 2.06 percent recorded in the first and second quarters of the referenced period as crude oil price plummeted from \$112 per barrel in 2014, to \$31 per barrel in January 2016 (NBS, 2016). The manufacturing sector saw a drop in the purchasing managers index (PMI) from 45.8 percent index points in May 2016, to 41.9 percent in June 2016 (CBN, 2016).

The Nigerian government is saddled with the responsibility of mitigating such calamitous business cycles through the proper usage of monetary policy. In November 2015, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), in its development finance function, launched the Anchor Borrowers Programme (ABP) with the intent to increase lending to sectors. In the drive to encourage local production of rice and other staple commodities, the Federal Government, using its monetary instruments, placed restrictions on the importation of rice and precluded access to foreign exchange for 43 items. These items are cold rolled steel sheets, rice, palm kernel/palm oil, vegetables/vegetable oils, margarine, meat and processed meat products, poultry, Indian incense, vegetables and processed vegetable products, roofing sheets, head pans, tinned fish in sauce, galvanized steel sheets, private airplanes, cement, metal boxes and containers, steel pipes, wire mesh, iron rods and reinforcing bars, wood particle boards and panels, plywood boards and panels, enamelware, wire rods, security and razor wire, furniture, wooden doors, toothpicks, tableware, glass and glassware, kitchen utensils, textiles, plastic and rubber products, clothes, milk, woven fabrics, maize, soap and cosmetics, Eurobond/foreign currency bonds/share, wrappers, tiles, plywood boards and panels, wood fiber boards and panels, and tomatoes/tomato pastes. The policy goal of precluding access to foreign exchange for these items was to encourage local manufacturing of these items, thereby increasing backward linkage to the agricultural sector for the necessary raw material inputs and forward linkage to the service sector. This strategic approach aimed at stimulating economic growth by promoting self-sufficiency and fostering a more robust domestic economy.

Among the major problems faced by the Nigerian economy are the inability to access foreign exchange to purchase needed raw materials, and the high cost of borrowing (Adegbe & Adeniji, 2013; Eniola, Entebang, & Sakariyau, 2015). To this end, the apex bank, in April 2017, introduced the Investors & Exporters (I & E) foreign exchange window and collapsed the various exchange rate windows as it continually

supplied foreign exchange to ensure its availability. This resulted in a significant improvement in the manufacturing sector as the PMI rose from 42 points in August 2016 to 57 points in February 2019. To ensure growth in credit and a reduction in interest rates, which would increase industry funding and raise the capacity of the manufacturing sector, the apex bank reduced the monetary policy rate by 100 basis points from 12.5 percent in July 2020 to 11.5 percent in September 2020.

Monetary policy is at the forefront of the management of the economy. It is for this reason that the monetary policy transmission mechanisms generated much interest. The Nigerian economy has performed poorly in recent times. Available data points to fluctuating growth in the real GDP of Nigeria. From the period of 2011 to 2014, the economy was growing at an average of 5 percent on a year-on-year (YoY) basis. In March 2014, the real GDP averaged 6.214 percent, increasing to 6.544 percent in June 2014 on a YoY basis. The Nigerian economy took a hit at the dawn of 2015, contracting by 3.964 percent in the first quarter of 2015 from 5.945 percent achieved in the last quarter of 2014. The downward trend in real growth continued into the future as growth dipped to 2.112 percent in the first quarter of 2016. In the second and third quarters of 2016, Nigeria recorded successive negative growth as the economy grew at -0.666 percent and -1.487 percent, respectively (NBS, 2016). The economy improved slightly from 0.716 percent in the second quarter of 2017 to 1.870 percent in the first quarter of 2020. The economic woes of the country were compounded as the economy witnessed its highest contraction in the second quarter of 2020, when it posted a negative growth rate of -6.104 percent (NBS, 2020).

However, the performance of the sectors contributing to economic growth casts doubt on the policy directions adopted by policymakers. Evidently, a distortion exists about the role of monetary policy in enhancing real sector growth. On the basis of the many uncertainties, this particular study investigated the effect of monetary policy coordination on economic growth in Nigeria using data sets 2002Q1 to 2022Q4.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Monetary Policy

Monetary policy is the deliberate use of monetary instruments (direct and indirect) at the disposal of monetary authorities such as the central bank, in order to achieve macroeconomic stability. Monetary policy is essentially the tool for executing the mandate of monetary and price stability. Monetary policy is essentially a program of

action undertaken by the monetary authorities, generally the central bank, to control and regulate the supply of money to the public and the flow of credit with a view to achieving predetermined macroeconomic goals (Dwivedi, 2005). Monetary policy has thus been known to be a vital instrument that a country can deploy for the maintenance of domestic prices and exchange rate stability as a critical condition for the achievement of sustainable economic growth and external viability (Adegbite & Alabi, 2013). Monetary policy may be inflationary or deflationary, depending on the economic condition of the country. Contractionary policy is enforced to squeeze down the money supply to curb inflation, and expansionary policy is to stimulate economic activity to combat unemployment in recessions (Adegbite & Alabi, 2013).

Empirical Literature Review

Modeled in line with the endogenous growth model, Adegboyo, Keji, and Fasina (2021) investigated the impact of government policies on economic growth in Nigeria using annual data from 1985 to 2020. Three government policies were focused on in their study and included monetary and trade policies. For government policies, they focused on the policy instruments of government expenditure and government revenue using money supply and interest rates to proxy monetary policy. In examining how trade policy affects economic growth, they adopted trade openness as a measure. The single-equation setup was analyzed using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) method. In exploring if there was a cointegrating relationship among the series, the bound test was applied and the result showed that the employed monetary and trade policy instruments and gross domestic product per capita (the proxy for economic growth) had a long-term relationship. Following the application of the ARDL method, the findings indicated that the fiscal policy variables of government expenditure and revenue had a positive and significant link with economic growth. Neither the monetary policy instrument of the interest rate nor the money supply, which had a negative impact on economic growth, were significant in causing changes in the level of output.

Adaramola and Dada (2020) investigated whether or not inflation has a detrimental effect on the economy of Nigeria. The study focused on the period between 1980 and 2018, primarily due to the inflation rate during the period caused by the rising crude oil price in the international market. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model set up to investigate the relationship between inflation and economic growth has real gross domestic product (as a proxy for economic growth) and the regressors of inflation, real interest rate, real exchange rate, degree of openness, money supply, and government consumption expenditure. The direction of causality among the

variables was determined using the pairwise Granger causality test. Using the bound test, it was confirmed that a long-term relationship exists between inflation and economic growth. The long-run ARDL result clearly showed that inflation and an increase in the real exchange rate had a detrimental effect on economic growth, as the impact they exerted on real GDP was negative and significant. Interestingly, the interest rate and money supply were reported to enhance economic growth. In terms of causal influence, it was reported that inflation and the degree of openness exhibited no causal effect on economic growth. It also revealed that government consumption, interest rates, and exchange rates had a unidirectional causal relationship with economic growth.

Tan, Mohamed, Habibullah and Chin (2020) used quarterly data from 1980Q1 to 2017Q1 to x-ray the relative effect of monetary and fiscal policies on economic growth in Singapore, Thailand and Malaysia. The reasons for their selection, according to the authors, were their common economic characteristics and similar demographic changes. In capturing the monetary policy stance, the money market rate was used, and for fiscal policy, they used government spending; and real gross domestic product was used in measuring economic growth. With concern about the long-run relationship, the models for the three countries were estimated within the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) framework. Their bound test supported the existence of a cointegrating relationship, as hinted by economic theory. The arguments from their ARDL result are that an increase in the money market rate significantly induced a fall in real gross domestic product. This result cut across all boards and was noticeable in Singapore, Thailand and Malaysia. The regression result showed a difference in how government spending affected economic growth across the three countries. In Malaysia and Singapore, increasing government spending will contract the level of output in the long-run. There was a deviation in the result for Thailand as government spending had a positive and significant link with economic growth. Their result buttressed the fact that, in addressing and achieving the macroeconomic goal of economic growth, monetary policy appeared to be more effective in Malaysia and Singapore. In Thailand, the most effective policy for driving economic growth was adjudged to be fiscal policy.

Shobande (2019) probed if the switch in monetary policy from direct to indirect methods affected industrial growth using Nigerian data covering the period from 1960 to 2015. This investigation used an econometric model with economic growth measured using gross domestic product and independent variables of money supply, trade balance, exchange rate, domestic credit, interest rate, and inflation. The

relationship between these variables was examined using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) method. The unit root test, which was carried out in line with the augmented Dickey-Fuller method, indicated that the variables were stationary and non-stationary of order one. The study confirmed using the bound test that gross domestic product, money supply, trade balance, exchange rate, domestic credit, interest rate, and inflation have equilibrium conditions binding them in the long-run. The estimation of the long model revealed a situation whereby increased money supply in Nigeria was associated with a decline in output. This result, which contradicted economic theory, was insignificant. Both domestic credit and interest rates, which stimulated economic growth in the long-run, were found to be significant. Like domestic credit and interest rates, trade balances promoted long-run economic growth but differed in significance as the positive effect was insignificant. Both the exchange rate and inflation were negatively associated with economic growth in the long-run and were also insignificant in affecting economic growth. In the short-run, an increase in domestic credit and interest rates led to a decline in economic growth, but the drop in output was observed after one lag.

Theoretical Review

The Anderson Jordan (A-J) Model

Since the Great Debate, a plethora of models that incorporate ideas of monetarism and Keynesian teachings have been introduced with the objective of determining which is effective in achieving economic growth. More recently, the focus has shifted away from arguments along these opposite poles of ideology, rallying to ascertain the impact of both policies on the sub-sectors of the economy, particularly those that contribute to economic growth. One of such models is the masterpiece developed at the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis by Anderson and Jordan, currently termed the A-J model. The A-J model was developed by Anderson and Jordan in 1968. The single equation underlying this model is cast as:

As seen above,

Y represents real GDP.

E summarizes government expenditure actions.

X summarizes government tax actions.

M denotes monetary actions, and

Z = other forces that influence government spending.

Equation 1 was expressed as:

= change in real GDP;

change in the money supply;

change in other forces influencing aggregate spending.

In the Anderson-Jordan model, all the variables are expressed in their first difference state, putting them into rate of growth form.

The Anderson-Jordan model is not without criticism. The model has been attacked for failing to measure what economic theory specifies. In addition, the use of a single equation has been faulted as it failed to address the issue of endogeneity.

Keynesian Theory of Money

In his infamous book entitled “The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money,” Keynes (1936) developed a monetary theory that rallied around output as opposed to price. The theory parts company with the classical view expressed in Fisher's equation, which argues in favor of a direct and proportionate relationship between money supply and price. Keynes (1936) opined that an indirect and non-proportional relationship exists between change in money supply and price level. Keynes (1936) argued a dichotomy exists between the relative price level (which is set by the demand for and supply of goods) and the absolute price level (determined by the demand for and supply of money). Going by this, the absolute price level (and not the relative price level) responds to changes in the money supply.

As posited by Keynes, under the assumption of less than full employment, the policy transmission mechanism flows from the financial sector to the real sector via the interest rate channel. According to Keynes, an increase in money supply is felt in the form of a decrease in interest rate, which snowballs into an increase in the volume of investment, thus raising effective demand through the instrumentality of the multiplier, causing output, income, and employment to increase (Gbosi, 2005).

The Classical Monetary Theory

The classical school evolved through the concerted efforts and contributions of economists like Jean-Baptiste Say, Adam Smith, David Ricardo, Pigou, and others who shared the same tenet. The classical model attempts to explain determination, savings, and investment with respect to money. The classical model of Say's law markets states that supply creates its own demand. Thus, classical economists believe that the economy automatically tends towards full employment level by laying emphasis on price level and on how best to eliminate inflation. The classical economists decided upon the quantity theory of money as the determinant of the general price level. This theory shows how money affects the economy. It may be considered in terms of the equation of exchange.

$MV = PY$

Two very similar quantity theory formulations were used to explain the level of price, viz. the transaction formulation or the Cambridge equation. In the transaction version associated with Fisher and Newcomb, these assumptions were made: that the quantity of money (m) is determined independently of other variables, the velocity of circulation (V) is taken as constant, and the volume of transactions (T) is also considered constant. Thus, based on price (p) and the assumption of full employment in the economy, the equation of exchange is given as follows:

$MV = PT$, which can readily establish that the level of price is a function of the supply of money. That is, $P = F(m)$, which implies that any change in price changes the money supply. In the cash balances version associated with Walras, Marshall, Wicksell, and Pigou, the neoclassical school (Cambridge School) changed the focus of the quantity theory without changing its underlying assumptions. This version focuses on the fraction (K) of income held as money balances. The Cambridge version can be expressed as:

$$M = kpy$$

Where K = fraction of income,

M = Quantity of money,

P = price level,

Y = value of goods and services

The K in the Cambridge equation is merely an inversion of V , the income velocity of money balances in the original formulation of quantity theory. This version directs attention to the determinants of demand for money, rather than the effects of changes in the supply of money (Anyanwu, 1993).

Methodology

Model Specification

The study employed quarterly frequency series data to investigate the effect of monetary policy on economic growth in Nigeria. The secondary data covered the period from 2002 Q1 to 2022 Q4. The choice of sample range is to reflect the indirect monetary regime in Nigeria. The quarterly frequency data for monetary policy variables such as monetary policy rate (MPR), broad money supply (MS), and nominal exchange rate (ECH) were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) official website and statistical bulletin. Quarterly data on public debt was sourced from the Debt Management Office (DMO); the non-monetary variables such as real gross domestic product (RGDP), consumer price index (CPI), and value-added of

real GDP were sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) website. The study used structural VAR methodology over the traditional VAR approach as it produces better and more robust results and infuses economic theory.

The study also examined the sectoral output effect of monetary policy by means of a structural vector autoregression (SVAR) model. In interacting with these variables in the VAR system, the variables in the system are treated as exogenous variables and expressed as functions of the lag variables of the independent variables. This assumption may not correctly apply in a system where changes in monetary instruments react to changes in other variables within the system. With structural VAR, it is possible to isolate such surprises or shocks and evaluate the response of other variables within the system when the economy is hit with such shocks. Implementing the structural VAR approach involves adopting two steps. The first is estimating the unrestricted VAR model while the second is the estimation of the structural factorization carried out by imposing certain restrictions on matrix A (the matrix that speaks to the contemporaneous relationship between the endogenous variables) based on economic intuition.

Assuming the Nigerian economy is described using the structural VAR (1) form equation below:

Where:

Z_t = is an $n \times 1$ vector of endogenous variables at time t ;

δ_0 = an $n \times 1$ vector of slope coefficients;

Z_{t-1} = the lag value of the endogenous variables included in the system; and

u_t = an $n \times 1$ structural shocks, where they are assumed to be independent of one another.

$A = n \times n$ matrix of contemporaneous relationship between the endogenous variables on which restrictions are placed so as to identify the structural model.

Assuming the endogenous variables are gross domestic product (GDP) and monetary policy rate (MPR), then equation (1) can be rewritten as:

$$GDP_t + \alpha_{12}MPR_t = \delta_{10} + \delta_{11}GDP_{t-1} + \delta_{12}MPR_{t-1} + u_t^{GDP} \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha_{21}GDP_t + MPR_t = \delta_{20} + \delta_{21}GDP_{t-1} + \delta_{22}MPR_{t-1} + u_t^{MPR} \quad (3)$$

u_t^{GDP} and u_t^{MPR} are output and monetary policy shocks which the study intends to identify and are serially uncorrelated.

For the monetary policy structural VAR model, matrix A would be a 6x6 matrix of contemporaneous relationship between the interest endogenous variables (sectoral output, monetary policy rate, money supply, and exchange rate) with the diagonal

elements being unity and the off-diagonal elements assuming arbitrary numbers. Z_t would be endogenous variables (sectoral output, monetary policy rate, money supply and exchange rate) observed in time t .

Equation (2) and (3) can be specified in matrix form as given below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \alpha_{12} \\ \alpha_{21} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} GDP_t \\ MPR_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{10} \\ \delta_{20} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{11} & \delta_{12} \\ \delta_{21} & \delta_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} GDP_{t-1} \\ MPR_{t-1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} u_t^{GDP} \\ u_t^{MPR} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) becomes:

$$AZ_t = \delta_0 + \delta_1 Z_{t-1} + u_t \quad (5)$$

Note that equation (5) cannot be estimated using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method due to the contemporaneous relationship between the endogenous variables and the fact that they are correlated with the structural errors (U^j). From equation (2) and (3), shocks to gross domestic product, denoted as u_t^{GDP} , affects gross domestic product directly and also affect monetary policy rate indirectly through the lag effect of gross domestic product in equation (3).

On the strength of this, equation (5) will be transformed to a reduced-form vector autoregression (VAR) model and OLS applied in estimating the forecast error from which the structural shocks can be retrieved. To do this, equation (5) shall be pre-multiplied by the inverse of matrix A . This gives the following:

$$A^{-1}AZ_t = A^{-1}\delta_0 + A^{-1}\delta_1 Z_{t-1} + A^{-1}u_t \quad (6)$$

Since the product of a matrix with its inverse is an identity matrix (that is, $A^{-1}A = I$), equation (6) becomes:

$$Z_t = \omega_0 + \omega_1 Z_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (7)$$

Where:

$$\omega_0 = A^{-1}\delta_0;$$

$$\omega_1 = A^{-1}\delta_1; \text{ and}$$

$$\varepsilon_t = A^{-1}u_t.$$

Equation (7) stipulates that Z_t (endogenous macroeconomic variables) depends on lags of itself and forecast errors (ε_t).

It is imperative to state that matrix A relates the forecast errors of the reduced-form VAR and the structural shocks, making the forecast errors linear combinations of the structural shocks u .

Thus;

$$\varepsilon_t = A^{-1}u_t$$

From equation (4), (6) and (7), the forecast errors for gross domestic product and monetary policy rate are given as:

$$\varepsilon_t^{GDP} = \frac{u_t^{GDP} - \delta_{12}u_t^{MPR}}{1 - \delta_{12}\delta_{21}}$$

$$\varepsilon_t^{MPR} = \frac{(-\delta_{12}u_t^{GDP} + u_t^{MPR})}{1 - \delta_{12}\delta_{21}}$$

Identification of the Structural VAR

One advantage of the structural VAR model in analysing the impact of monetary policy on the economy is that, the structural VAR model isolates structural shocks (monetary policy rate shocks, money supply shocks, exchange rate shocks, government spending shocks, government revenue shocks, public debt shocks, among others) and allows tracing out the dynamics of the variables included in the vector autoregression (VAR) after one of those shocks hits the economy. In obtaining the structural shocks, restrictions need to be placed on matrix A (the matrix that informs on the contemporaneous relationship between the variables in the system) based on economic theory. The process of placing restriction on matrix A is called identification.

In retrieving the structural model, shocks and contemporaneous relationship among the variables, the reduced-form VAR is multiplied by A. This gives:

$$Z_t = \omega_0 + \omega_1 Z_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (8)$$

$$AZ_t = A\omega_0 + A\omega_1 Z_{t-1} + A\varepsilon_t \quad (9)$$

But:

$$\omega_0 = A^{-1}\delta_0;$$

$$\omega_1 = A^{-1}\delta_1; \text{ and}$$

$$\varepsilon_t = A^{-1}u_t.$$

This gives:

$$AZ_t = \delta_0 + \delta_1 Z_{t-1} + u_t \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Since } AA^{-1}\delta_0 = \delta_0$$

Generally, the reduced-form VAR is:

$$Z_t = \omega_0 + \omega_1 Z_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (11)$$

Assuming the endogenous variables are gross domestic product (GDP) and monetary policy rate (MPR), equation (8) becomes:

$$GDP_t = \omega_{10} + \omega_{11}GDP_{t-1} + \omega_{12}MPR_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t^{GDP} \quad (12)$$

$$MPR_t = \omega_{20} + \omega_{21}GDP_{t-1} + \omega_{22}MPR_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t^{MPR} \quad (13)$$

The structural VAR model is:

$$GDP_t + \alpha_{12}MPR_t = \delta_{10} + \delta_{11}GDP_{t-1} + \delta_{12}MPR_{t-1} + u_t^{GDP} \quad (14)$$

$$\alpha_{21}GDP_t + MPR_t = \delta_{20} + \delta_{21}GDP_{t-1} + \delta_{22}MPR_{t-1} + u_t^{MPR} \quad (15)$$

As clearly shown from equation (12) and (13), the unknown parameters are numbered nine (9), that is, six (6) coefficients, two (2) variances, and one (1) covariance. In the structural VAR model – equation 14 and 15 – there are ten (10) unknowns: eight (8) parameters and two (2) variances. With the structural shocks (u_t^{GDP} and u_t^{MPR}) assumed to be independent, the covariance is zero.

Since the parameters to be estimated from the reduced-form VAR is less than those in the structural VAR model, the VAR model is deemed unidentified. With this, recovering the structural shocks, contemporaneous relationship among the variables and structural model becomes difficult. For emphasis, the estimation of the structural parameters of the VAR model as specified in equation 14 and 15, requires the model to be either identified or over-identified. For exact identification, the number of parameters in the structural VAR must be equal to those in the reduced-form VAR model. The identification of the structural VAR model requires $\frac{m(m-1)}{2}$ imposing restrictions on matrix A or on the contemporaneous relationship among the variables, where m represents the number of endogenous variables within the VAR system. The restriction(s) are imposed based on economic theory, hence, the superiority of the structural VAR model over the traditional VAR model. In matrix A, one is normalized as the coefficients on the diagonals, while zero denotes no contemporaneous relationship between the two variables.

In the hypothetical model, if a_{12} is said to be zero, then, the restriction imposed is that gross domestic product (GDP) is not contemporaneously affected by a shock to monetary policy rate, but with a lag by a shock to monetary policy rate (MPR). Similarly, it indicates that monetary policy rate reacts contemporaneously to shocks or changes in gross domestic product (GDP).

Equation 14 and 15 becomes:

$$GDP_t = \delta_{10} + \delta_{11}GDP_{t-1} + \delta_{12}MPR_{t-1} + u_t^{GDP} \quad (16)$$

$$\alpha_{21}GDP_t + MPR_t = \delta_{20} + \delta_{21}GDP_{t-1} + \delta_{22}MPR_{t-1} + u_t^{MPR} \quad (17)$$

The imposition of the restriction that gross domestic product does not react contemporaneously to changes in monetary policy rate ensures the structural VAR is identified, and the contemporaneous relationship and structural shocks can be recovered. Placing restrictions on matrix A presupposes that there is restriction on the relationship between the forecast errors and the structural shocks. This means that the forecast error of gross domestic product (GDP) is equal to the structural shocks of gross domestic product. Hence;

$$\varepsilon_t^{GDP} = u_t^{GDP}$$

The structural VAR model becomes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} GDP_t \\ MPR_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{10} & 0 \\ -\alpha_{21}\delta_{10} & \delta_{20} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{11} & \delta_{12} \\ -\alpha_{21}\delta_{11} + \delta_{12} & -\alpha_{21}\delta_{21}\delta_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} GDP_{t-1} \\ MPR_{t-1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} u_t^{GDP} \\ -\alpha_{21}u_t^{GDP} + u_t^{MPR} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

The gross domestic product shocks (u_t^{GDP}) and monetary policy rate shocks (u_t^{MPR}) are retrieved as follows:

$$\varepsilon_t^{GDP} = u_t^{GDP}$$

The monetary policy rate shocks are given as:

$$\varepsilon_t^{MPR} = -\alpha_{21}u_t^{GDP} + u_t^{MPR}$$

Re-arranging;

$$u_t^{MPR} = \varepsilon_t^{MPR} + \alpha_{21}u_t^{GDP}$$

But;

$$\varepsilon_t^{GDP} = u_t^{GDP}$$

Thus:

$$u_t^{MPR} = \varepsilon_t^{MPR} + \alpha_{21}\varepsilon_t^{GDP}$$

Identification of the Monetary Policy Shocks

In analysing the response of real sector output to monetary shocks, this study employed five (5) structural VAR variables, namely net gross domestic product, monetary policy rate, money supply, exchange rate and sectoral output following a non-recursive identification procedure as restrictions is placed on the variables contained in the system (as reflected in equation 19).

The last equation is the real GDP where the assumption is that the real GDP is affected contemporaneously by net gross domestic product, monetary policy rate and money supply. This theoretical backing for this is based on the IS-LM framework.

For the monetary policy model, the individual sectoral structural VAR model is given below:

$$AZ_t = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \alpha_{14} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \alpha_{51} & \alpha_{52} & \alpha_{54} & \alpha_{54} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Y_i - Y_{it} \\ MPR \\ MS \\ ECH \\ Y_t \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Y_i = real GDP

$Y_i - Y_{it}$ = total output less real sector output

Matrix A = the contemporaneous relationship between the endogenous variables, with restriction place based on economic intuitions.

In providing insight into the effect of monetary policy variables on real sector, the study intends to estimate the following models within the structural VAR framework.

Real GDP Shock

The effect of monetary policy variables on real GDP is given as:

$$x_t = M(L)x_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (20)$$

Where $x_t = f(MPR, MS, ECH, Y_T - R_{At}, R_{At})$

x_t = an $n \times 1$ vector of endogenous variables at time t ,

$M(L)$ = matrix polynomial in the lagged operator L ;

ε_t = an $n \times 1$ structural shocks; and

Y_A = real GDP

Following restrictions on the contemporaneous matrix, the effect of monetary policy variables on real GDP is captured below:

$$AZ_t = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \alpha_{14} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \alpha_{51} & \alpha_{52} & \alpha_{54} & \alpha_{54} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Y_T - R_{At} \\ MPR \\ MS \\ ECH \\ R_{At} \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

Y_A = real GDP

$Y_T - Y_{At}$ = total GDP less real GDP

Matrix A = the contemporaneous relationship between the endogenous variables, with restriction place based on economic intuitions.

Description of Variables

Given that the variables to be included in the structural VAR model are deemed to be endogenous and the focus of the study is on the sectoral output effect of monetary

policies, the following dependent and independent variables were selected for this study:

Dependent Variable

Real (GDP): Real output, also known as real GDP, is the value of goods and services produced by an economy at constant prices. It adjusts for changes in the price level or inflation over time.

Independent Variables

i. Monetary Policy Rate (MPR)

This refers to the rate at which the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) lends to deposit money banks (DMBs) and other clients. An increase in MPR typifies a contraction in the money supply, which reduces liquidity, consumption and investment spending; future cash flows of companies, and the performance of industries and the economy at large. The reverse happens when the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) cuts down on its policy rate.

ii. Money Supply (MS)

This refers to the amount of money in circulation in an economy at a given time period. Money supply has been employed by monetary authorities to change the outlook of an economy as it affects investment and consumption spending. For this study, money supply is factored as a monetary policy instrument and enters the structural VAR (SVAR) model as an endogenous variable.

iii. Exchange Rate (ECH)

This defines the value of the naira in terms of the United States dollar. The exchange rate of the naira refers to the amount of the naira that will be exchanged to get one United States dollar in the foreign exchange market. The exchange rate shall be incorporated into the model to capture the interaction between monetary policy and the foreign exchange market. An increase in the exchange rate of the naira to the dollar signals a weak naira or depreciation of the naira against the United States dollar, and should ordinarily stimulate aggregate demand and output due to increased exports as Nigerian goods and services become less expensive in the international market. In the study, the official exchange rate of the naira against the United States dollar was used to measure the exchange rate.

Univariate Unit Root Result

Variable	ADF			PP		KPSS		I(d)
	Level	FD	SD	Level	FD	Level	FD	
.	0.0975	-1.4594	-30.3119***	-0.2145	-29.7984***	1.1139	0.1323**	I(1)
.	-2.8527	-5.3739***	-	-2.5998	-5.4435***	-	-	I(1)
.	-2.3304	-7.0302***	-	-2.1700	-7.0426***	-	-	I(1)
h.	0.6165	-7.8034***	-	0.5058	-7.7728***	-	-	I(1)

Note: *, ** & *** indicate significance at 10%, 5%, & 1%; FD = first difference; SD = second difference; ADF = Augmented Dickey-Fuller; PP = Phillip-Perron

Source: Author's computation (2023).

The table presents the ADF and PP tests and their critical values. The first difference unit root results, based on the ADF procedures, indicate that monetary policy rate, money supply, and exchange rate are first difference stationary or I(1) when the Phillip-Perron method was applied to validate the outcome of the ADF test. These suggests that both the augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillip-Perron agree on the distribution of monetary policy rate, money supply and exchange rate being integrated of order one.

VAR Lags Selection

This study adopted a scientific process in determining the number of lags to be included in the monetary policy-real GDP model.

Lag Selection.

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	250.8227	NA	1.07E-09	-6.4690	-6.3156	-6.4077
1	306.991	103.4678	4.71E-10	-7.2892	-6.3692	-6.9215
2	379.2815	123.6548	1.37E-10	-8.5337	-6.8470	-7.8596
3	517.8348	218.7684	7.04E-12	-11.522	-9.0685	-10.5415
4	633.574	167.5173*	6.74e-13*	-13.9098*	-10.6897*	-12.6229*
5	652.3755	24.7387	8.51E-13	-13.7467	-9.7599	-12.1534
6	666.5555	16.7921	1.26E-12	-13.462	-8.7085	-11.5623
7	696.4679	31.4867	1.30E-12	-13.5913	-8.0711	-11.3851

Note: * lag selected by criterion

For the monetary policy-real GDP model, incorporating the monetary policy rate, money supply, and exchange rate as interest variables, the report on the number of lags included in the model is presented below. The lag length of 4 quarters was based on the Akaike information criterion (AIC). Other information criteria such as the

Schwarz information criteria (SC) and Hanaan-Quinn (HQ), also suggested a lag length of four (4) quarters. This suggests that a vector autoregression model of lag 4, VAR (4), was estimated for the monetary policy-real GDP model.

Contemporaneous Coefficient

The structural vector autoregression (SVAR) model differs from the traditional VAR model as it incorporates the contemporaneous relationship among the interest variables when modelling the effect of a shock in a particular variable on other variables in the system. The underpinning of the structural VAR model is that the variables in the system are endogenous, suggesting that each variable has an equation detailing the nature of its relationship with other variables in the system. The result of the short-run contemporaneous relationship for the monetary policy-real GDP structural model are under the variables ordering of net-gross domestic product (GDP), monetary policy rate, money supply, exchange rate, and real GDP gross domestic product.

Structural Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variables					
Variables	Net GDP	MPR	MS	ECH	RGDP
Net GDP	1				
MPR	-2.065 (4.2871)	1			
MS	0.8208*** (0.2634)	-0.0112 (0.0069)	1		
ECH	0.4918 (0.3357)	-0.0125 (0.0084)	0.1912 (0.1353)	1	
RGDP	0.0515 (0.0069)	0.0001 (0.0019)	-0.1077*** (0.0318)	-0.0271 (0.0261)	1

Note: Reported in parentheses are standard errors from MLE

Source: Author's compilation (2023)

To examine the nature of contemporaneous relationships among the structural VAR variables, the study imposed restrictions on matrix A, relying mainly on economic theory. For the structural VAR model that tries to explain how monetary policy variables affect the real GDP, the study employed five variables, which gave rise to five equations. The rows represent the various equations: the net GDP equation, the monetary policy rate equation, the money supply equation, the exchange rate

equation, and the real GDP equation. The column attests to the contemporaneous effect of the endogenous variables on each of the equations, as ordered based on economic theory.

The monetary policy equation reveals that the net gross domestic product elasticity of MPR is negative. This indicates that an increase in economic activities leads to a reduction in the monetary policy rate. This contemporaneous relationship between monetary policy rate and net GDP is consistent with economic theories as policy makers try to sustain or increase the momentum of economic activities when output begins to increase by reducing the monetary policy rate to further stimulate aggregate demand, as a decrease in the policy rate fosters consumption and investment spending due to a reduction in the cost of borrowing. The negative contemporaneous effect of net GDP on the monetary policy rate is insignificant, indicating that the monetary policy authority in Nigeria, that is, the Central Bank of Nigeria, usually does not consider the level of economic activities when setting the benchmark rate (monetary policy rate), reemphasizing the price stability mandate of the Central Bank of Nigeria.

The coefficient of 0.8208 for net GDP in the money supply equation indicates that the money supply has a contemporaneous increase after an increase in net GDP or economic activities. The positive effect of net GDP on money supply is significant and in line with theory, as an increase in economic output indicates an increase in factor income and money supply as there is more cash in the hands of economic agents and they increase their demand deposits.

In the exchange rate equation, the contemporaneous effect of net GDP and money supply is positive and is consistent with economic theory. The parameter of monetary policy rate in the exchange rate equation has the correct negative sign, as suggested by theory. An increase in net GDP indicates increased income for economic agents, which may further fuel imports, causing a depreciation of the naira against the US dollar. The contemporaneous effect of all three endogenous variables on the exchange rate is insignificant.

In the real GDP equation, the coefficients of 0.0515 for net GDP and 0.0001 for monetary policy rate indicate that the contemporaneous effect of net GDP and monetary policy rate on real GDP is positive, as increases in both variables cause real GDP to increase. The positive contemporaneous effect of the endogenous variables of net GDP on real GDP is theoretically consistent, as an increase in net GDP will

have a positive spillover effect on real GDP output. The positive contemporaneous effect of the monetary policy rate on real GDP does not match the theoretical positive sign. Both net GDP and the monetary policy rate were insignificant in affecting real GDP contemporaneously. This means real GDP is not responsive to immediate changes in net GDP and the monetary policy rate. The money supply elasticity of the exchange rate is negative and significant. This result is theoretically inconsistent, as an increase in the money supply will cause real GDP output to decline, violating the expected positive relationship. In the real GDP equation, the exchange rate had a negative contemporaneous effect on real GDP output, suggesting that real GDP output declines when the naira depreciates against the US dollar. This negative contemporaneous relationship between the exchange rate and real GDP is insignificant.

Impulse Response Function

In this section, the impulse response function (IRF) was estimated with the intention of explaining the dynamic responses to real GDP shocks (the monetary policy variables included in the structural VAR system). The IRF was used to trace the response of real GDP to monetary policy rate shocks, money supply shocks, exchange rate shocks, and output shocks. Using the IRF method, the study is able to show the dynamic response of current and future values of real GDP to one unit change in the current value of one structural shock, assuming other structural shocks remain constant.

Real GDP Output Response to Exchange Rate Shock

**Response of LRGDP to Shock3
using Structural VAR Factors**

Real GDP Output Response to Money Supply Shock

**Response of LRGDP to Shock4
using Structural VAR Factors**

Real GDP Output Response to Exchange Rate Shock

Response of LRGDP to Shock5 using Structural VAR Factors

Real GDP Output Response to Own Shock

The study began by estimating the structural impulse response function to shocks to the monetary policy variables and the response of the real GDP to these shocks. The graphics above are the depiction of how real GDP responds when there is a shock to monetary policy rate (shock 2), money supply (shock 3), exchange rate (shock 4), and own shock (shock 5). The shock to these variables can be positive or negative, with the nature of the shocks dependent on the structural variables. This reveals that a positive shock to the monetary policy rate, which is an indication of monetary policy tightening or the monetary policy squeezing the liquidity level in the country, causes real GDP output to contract up to the second quarter. Activities in real GDP recover in the third quarter as real GDP output increases from the dip that occurred from the first quarter to the second quarter. The cycle of downturn and recovery was re-enacted in the third and fourth quarters as activities in the real GDP sector contracted on the heels of tightening money policy through raising the monetary policy rate. The downturn in real GDP was upended as activities in the sector picked up, with real GDP output growing positively and remaining so up to the seventh quarter. Positive shocks to the money supply (shock 3) produced a decline in real GDP output up to the second quarter, but the decline did not encroach into negative territory. With real GDP output contracting mildly by the end of the second and fourth quarters, the level

of real GDP output was up strongly from the fourth to fifth quarters. The figure shows that the response of real GDP output to money supply shocks was stable and positive for most of the quarters. The figure reveals that real GDP output remains positive and fairly stable when the economy is hit with a positive exchange rate shock. This positive response of real GDP output to a positive exchange rate shock, an indication that the naira depreciates against the US dollar, is theoretically valid as a weakened currency drives output production as domestic goods become cheap for foreigners. The figure that presents the IRF for own shocks reveals a positive response of real GDP output for own shocks, as real GDP output only contracted in the third and seventh quarters.

Forecast Error Variance Decomposition

With the structural VAR models identified and the contemporaneous or structural parameters recovered, it becomes imperative to determine the proportion of variation in sectoral output caused by monetary policy variables. To do this, the study employed structural forecast error variance decomposition (SFEVD) analysis. With the analysis, the study is able to show the proportions of variation in real GDP output caused by the sectors and the variations caused by other structural shocks (, and) in the system. With the SFEVD, the study can obtain information on the importance of each structural shock. With the SFEVD analysis, the proportion of innovations in real GDP output is accounted for by the monetary policy rate, money supply, and exchange rate at different quarters.

Variance Decomposition of Real GDP

Variance Decomposition of Real GDP

Period	S.E.	Shock1	Shock2	Shock3	Shock4	Shock5
1	0.0193	4.1698	0.5054	11.2014	1.1388	82.9844
2	0.0207	4.1079	1.3312	11.3499	1.1375	82.0733
3	0.0211	4.4216	1.6168	11.3827	1.1145	81.4641
4	0.0222	5.3388	2.8415	11.1662	1.1069	79.5463
5	0.0259	4.1456	2.0726	12.4596	1.6186	79.7033
6	0.0270	4.1401	2.0813	12.3594	1.7470	79.6719
7	0.0274	4.4163	2.0513	12.0918	1.9574	79.4829
8	0.0283	5.7668	2.2160	11.9074	1.9301	78.1794
9	0.0306	4.4839	1.8504	12.2182	2.2319	79.2154
10	0.0315	4.5403	1.9299	12.1130	2.2219	79.1946

Note: Shock 1 = net GDP shock; Shock 2 = monetary policy rate shocks; shock 3 = money supply shock; shock 4 = exchange rate shocks and shock 5 = own shock

Source: Author's computation (2023)

The figure shows the variance decomposition of real GDP over a period of 10 quarters. The figure reveals the decomposition of the variation in real GDP output into components shocks: net GDP shocks, monetary policy rate shocks, money supply shocks, and own shocks. The figure reveals that the highest factor influencing variation in real GDP output is own shocks. This influence is observable over the short and medium runs. In the first quarter, real GDP output explained 82.9844% of their forecast error variance. In addition, net GDP shock accounts for 4.1698% of the variation in real GDP output, monetary policy rate accounts for 0.5054%, money supply shock explains 11.144% of the real GDP output variation, and exchange rate accounts for 1.1388% of total variations in real GDP output in the first quarter.

The result reveals that the proportion of own shocks in explaining fluctuation in real GDP output declines in the medium term and reduces to 78.1794% in the eighth quarter, increasing slightly to 79.1946% in the tenth quarter, or after two years. More so, the fluctuation in real GDP output due to money supply shocks, increases in the medium term, rising to 12.4596% in the fourth quarter. In the long term, the proportion of variation in real GDP output caused by shocks to the money supply begins to decrease and reduces to 12.1130% in the tenth quarter. Table 4.10 reveals that shocks to the monetary policy rate contribute less than 3% to the fluctuation in real GDP output. The contribution of the monetary policy rate to variations in real GDP output increased from 0.5054% in the first quarter to 2.8415% in the fourth quarter. The fluctuation in real GDP output due to shocks to the monetary policy rate declined after the 4th quarter to 1.9299% in the tenth quarter. Table 4.10 reports the increasing contribution of money supply shocks to forecast error variance in real GDP output as it increased from 1.1388% in the first quarter to 2.2219% in the tenth quarter.

From the result of Table 4.10, it is evident that, in terms of transmission channels of monetary policy, money supply shocks (shock 3) explain more fluctuation in real GDP output than monetary policy rate shocks and exchange rate shocks.

Summary of the Study

In a bid to investigate the impact of monetary policies on sectoral output, the study employed the monetary policy variables of monetary policy rate, money supply and exchange rate. The policy variables of government expenditure, tax revenue, and public debt were also used. The study used secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) official website and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin. The data used was quarterly information and covered 84 quarters, focusing on the period from 2002 Q1 to 2022 Q4. The study employed the structural

vector autoregression (SVAR) model to analyze the effect of monetary policy shocks on real GDP. The SVAR method affords one the ability to identify purely exogenous innovations and examine the effect on the endogenous variables in our system when such exogenous shocks hit the economy. The study employed the impulse response function (IRF) to trace the effect of shock on a variable and analyse the response of other variables in the system to such shock. In addition, the forecast error variance decomposition (FEVD) method was employed to analyse the proportion of variability in a particular variable due to shocks to other endogenous variables in the system.

The major findings of this study are summarized as follows:

- i. The monetary policy rate has a positive and insignificant impact on output in Nigeria.
- ii. The money supply was found to have a negative and significant impact on real GDP.
- iii. Money supply shocks contribute at least 11% to the variability in real GDP.
- iv. The study observed that appreciation of the exchange of the naira insignificantly promotes growth in real GDP.

Conclusion

The clamor for the diversification of the Nigerian economy away from the black gold into sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and service sectors is hinged on the trio being key propellers of growth and welfare advancement in any state. The valid argument proposed is that the ills faced by Nigeria in the form of rising unemployment levels, inflation rates, widespread poverty, income inequality, and the balance of payments deficit can be addressed or corrected if continuous growth can be achieved in the economy. The growth in these sectors output is dependent on certain supporting physical infrastructure such as a good transport system, energy, accessibility to funds, increased ease of doing business, and a growth-induced tax system, which fall within the jurisdiction of the monetary system. On the strength of this, the study examined the effect of monetary policy on economic growth within the structural vector autoregression (SVAR) framework. Therefore, the study concludes that economic growth responds to shocks to the money supply and monetary policy rate.

Recommendations

- i. It is proposed that the policy direction of the apex bank should be toward reducing the monetary policy rate (MPR), as this will make credit available to

- real sector investors and resolve the credit constraint militating output expansion.
- ii. The insignificant impact of money supply on output could result from the structure of the economy, which depends heavily on imports to acquire necessary raw materials.
 - iii. The Central Bank of Nigeria should implement policies to address the frequent fluctuations in the exchange rate value of the naira and protect investors.
 - iv. Proper management of the reserves is advised in order to ensure the stability of the exchange rate value of the naira.
 - v. The Federal Government should raise its capital expenditure from the paltry 15 percent of total budgetary expenditure to 45 percent to prop up output.

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